

HOW DO PEOPLE ASSESS COMPUTER GENERATED EXPRESSIVE MUSIC PERFORMANCES?

Sergio Canazza

CSC-DEI, Univ. Padova
canazza@dei.unipd.it

Giovanni De Poli

CSC-DEI, Univ. Padova
depoli@dei.unipd.it

Antonio Rodà

CSC-DEI, Univ. Padova
roda@dei.unipd.it

ABSTRACT

Music performance has been studied since long time and several computational systems were developed for generating expressive music performances. These models are generally evaluated by comparing their predictions with actual performances, both from a quantitative and a subjective point of view, often focusing on very specific aspects of the model. However little is known about how listeners evaluate the generated performances and which are the factors influencing their judgement and appreciation.

In this paper we present two experiments, conducted during two dedicated workshops, to start understanding how the audience judges the entire performances. In particular we analyzed possible different preferences and expectations of the listeners and influencing factors, such as cognitive styles.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many researchers analyzed and modeled human performance of musical scores, and the results led to the development of several computational systems for the so called computer generated expressive music performance (see e.g. [1] and [2] for a review). This area has drawn much attention from computer science researchers because of the challenge of emulating human competence. These systems are generally evaluated by comparing their predictions with actual performances, both from a quantitative and a subjective point of view, often focusing on very specific aspects of the model, such as a single rule, a phrasing rendering, a conveyed emotion [3]. The main evaluation aim is to validate or improve the system. However little is known how listeners evaluate the generated performances and which are the factors influencing their judgement and appreciation.

In order to analyze more deeply the subjective effectiveness of computer generated performances, the Performance Rendering Contest (Rencon) was initiated in 2002 [4] by Katayose and colleagues as a form of competition among different systems. During the years the Rencon contest evolved toward a more structured format. Now it is conducted in two stages. In the first one, a panel of experts rates both the scientific novelty of the entrant systems and

their usefulness. In the second one, the performances generated during a dedicated workshop are openly evaluated by the audience and Internet viewers (see [5] for details).

The purpose of this paper is to investigate an aspect which has been overlooked by recent research, i.e. how subjects evaluate computer generated performances. Only recently has empirical research started to investigate the factors that influence human performance evaluations and the interactions among these factors. This research has typically focused on formal settings, such as competitions, or on educational practices [6–8]. It is thus worth studying more in detail how listeners evaluate and appreciate automatic performances, which factors influence their preferences and expectation. To this purpose we present a preliminary experiment carried out during Rencon-SMC11, which will be summarized in section 3, and a second one carried out during the meeting of the musicological society of Italy (GATM) on April 2012. In particular we analyze possible different preferences and expectations of the listeners and influencing factors, such as cognitive styles [9].

2. MUSIC APPRECIATION AND COGNITIVE STYLES

Individuals are different and we could therefore expect them to react differently to music just as they react differently to other stimuli. Research on individual differences has already explained between-person differences to identical psychological tasks. These individual differences also affect the way we react to music. Recently, Kreutz et al. [9] demonstrated the existence of top-down strategies during listening to music using a questionnaire survey. They found that listeners may be classified as *music-empathizers* (ME) when they focus on the affective aspects of the music and try to get tuned to the emotions of the composer or as *music-systemizers* (MS) who are rather interested in finding structures and organization behind the music. Moreover they developed an instrument for the measurement of music empathizing. This scale was designed to investigate empathy as a cognitive style of processing music, rather than as a general trait. The authors reported that their scales were found to be internally consistent and reliable and results aligned with that of the general empathy scale [9]. Using this scale, it was found that listeners who enjoy computer music based genres demonstrated a trend towards a higher mean score on the music-systemizing scale than those who enjoy love songs [10].

Figure 1. Boxplot of performance ratings of Rencon-SMC11 participants.

We can hypothesize that the cognitive style also may influence the preferences when evaluating computer generated performances. To this purpose we submitted of the participants of our experiment the questionnaire in order to measure their cognitive style.

3. RENCON-SMC11 EXPERIMENT

3.1 Material and method

During the final phase of Rencon-SMC11, five systems generated two expressive performances and were evaluated by the workshop attendants, who were experts on Sound and Music Computing. The five systems were:

- E1 uses two algorithms: *YQX* [11], developed by Dept. of Computational Perception, J. Kepler University, Linz (Austria) for tempo and Basis mixer [12] for dynamics;
- E2 *CaRo 2.0*, developed by the Sound and Music Computing group, Dept. of Information Engineering, University of Padova (Italy) [2];
- E3 *DirectorMusices*, developed by the Music Acoustics Group, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm (Sweden) [13];
- E4 *VirtualPhilharmony*, developed by Katayose Lab., Dept. of Human and Systems Interaction, Kwansei Gakuin University (Japan) [14].
- E5 *Shunji*, developed by Katayose Lab., Dept. of Human and Systems Interaction, Kwansei Gakuin University (Japan) [15].

E1, E3, E5 are autonomous systems, while E2 and E4 are interactive performance systems [5].

The method and the results of the contest are discussed in [3, 5]; a new analysis of the ratings is presented below.

Just after the audience listened and evaluated the automatic performances, we distributed a questionnaire to the

attendees. The purpose was to collect more information on the criteria used by the adjudicators and suggestions for future Rencon contests.

3.2 Results

The results are discussed in [5]. Here we summarize the most interesting results for our aims.

3.2.1 Analysis of ratings

Fig. 1 shows the box plot of ratings with estimated density traces. All the distributions are unimodal.

In order to explore the preferences of the listeners, we projected each listener rating on a 2D plane, by a PCA of the expressed evaluations of the system performances; the first two components explains respectively 46,4% and 20,7% of the total variance (Fig. 2). We may observe that the point are very scattered in the plane and don't show any clustering. Then we evaluated the correlation among each performance and the two-dimensional coordinates of the listeners. Fig. 2 shows the direction and strength of the maximal correlation of the listener preferences with the PCA positions of the performances. We may observe that the judgements of Caro system tend to be orthogonal to the Shunji one and that some subjects tend to evaluate similarly Caro and YQX systems, while others tend to agree in the evaluations of DirectorMusices and VirtualPhilharmony.

Figure 2. Biplot of a Principal Component Analysis of the performances ratings of Rencon-SMC11 participants. Numbers represent the ID of each listener, whereas arrows represent the correlation among the systems.

3.2.2 Analysis of listeners' preferences

The first question was intended to identify the expectation level of the listeners and was formulated as follows: *Your evaluation was made with reference to:* with three alternative answers: masters degree music student, music teacher, or top-level performer. The majority (58.3%) of the participants, who answered this question, indicated masters degree student as the reference used in their performance evaluations, while professional performers and music teachers were specified by 30.6% and 11.1% of the

respondents, respectively. Thus, we can conclude that although the majority of the participants realistically expected a student-quality performance, approximately 2/5 of the participants had higher expectations. This expectation might be influenced by the contest setting and by the qualification level of the entrants, which may induce high expectations in the attendants. The non-answer rate of 10% may indicate that the question was not fully understood, and thus it was not included in the next experiment.

n.	Factors influencing the judgment	Freq.
b1	is able to highlight elements related to the musical structure (phrasing, counterpoint)	77.5%
b2	contains unexpected but interesting choices	40.0%
b3	is consistent with the suitable musical style (from an historical point of view)	52.5%
b4	is consistent with the favorite style (from a subjective point of view)	12.5%
b5	is consistent with the style of a famous performer	5.0%
b6	is able to convey emotional content	57.5%
b7	contains evident musical errors (that a human would never perform)	52.5%
b8	is consistent with the actual performance context (concert hall, classroom, or automatic performance contest)	7.5%

Table 1. Frequency of the main factors influencing the judgment of Rencon-SMC11 participants.

The second question, *Which of the following are the main factors that influenced your judgment?*, was intended to encourage subjects to reflect on the criteria that they used, either consciously or subconsciously. Different possible factors were proposed, and the subjects were told that they could select more than one option. The proposed factors tended to cover technical, interpretative/communicative, and stylistic aspects of the performances. The frequency of responses is reported in Tab. 1. We can observe that technical and interpretative/communicative factors predominate, whereas stylistic factors are much less frequently considered. No significant correlations were found between the answers to these questions and musical training, age, or gender.

Figure 3 shows the biplot of the Correspondence Analysis of these factors, as expressed by Rencon-SMC11 participants. The first two components explain 24.7% and 22.2% of total variance. We can notice that the main difference is due by factors b4, b5 and b8, which were less frequently indicated by attendants and were probably interpreted as mutually exclusive. A more interesting differentiation is characterized by factors b1, b2 and b3 respectively. We can hypothesize that they may contribute to diverse attitudes in evaluating generated performance. Instead factors b6 and b7 are almost superimposed, even if they represent two quite different assessment categories i.e. emotional vs. technical. We can conjecture that both factors are felt equally important in the assessment.

Figure 3. Biplot of a correspondence analysis of the factors influencing the judgement of Rencon-SMC11 participants.

4. GATM 2012 EXPERIMENT

4.1 Participants

On Sunday, 22nd, April, 2012 at Liszt Institute in Bologna (Italy) the annual assembly of the Italian Analysis and Music Theory Group (*Gruppo Analisi e Teoria Musicale*, GATM) was held. In that occasion, a workshop on musical performance analysis took place. This workshop focused on expressive performance rendering computer systems. All the participants were Italian musicologists, specialized in musical analysis. Total = 23; 17 male; 6 female; 9 younger (≤ 50 years); 14 older (> 50 years).

The assessors' age is surveyed in categories (21-30; 31-40; 41-50; ...). The mean age falls in the interval 51-60 years; the overall range is between 31-40 to 71-80 years.

4.2 Materials

Four different performances of a short classical musical piece were proposed to the workshop participants. Several Sonatas (by Cherubini, Clementi, Gotifredo Ferrari da Rovereto, Kuhlau and Beethoven) were considered. First of all, the first movements (exposure of Sonata form) were discarded because it is both too long and quite trivial. At the end, the Op. 88, n. 3, *Allegro Burlesco* by Kuhlau was chosen because it lasts just over two minutes, it is not too complex and it possesses an expressive character.

The authors asked the teams classified in the first four positions at the final phase of Rencon-SMC11 to prepare the stimuli (files in MIDI format) using their systems for automatic expressive performance. All the four MIDI files were played by the same piano Yamaha Disklavier MarkIV. Finally, they were recorded by two AKG 414 microphones and transferred to the digital domain by a FireFace 800 A/D converter (96kHz, 24bit). The systems E1-E4 of the Rencon-SMC11 Experiment were used. E1 used Basis mixer [12] for dynamics, tempo, and articulation.

Figure 4. Boxplot of performance ratings in GATM experiment. Performance E2 shows a bimodal distribution.

4.3 Method

The attendees were invited to rate each stimulus and to fill an assessment questionnaire (see Appendix A), which was divided into three parts. At the end of the workshop the results were presented and discussed. Then, we presented the mathematical models used in the four performance rendering systems and communicated the ranking of the performances. Finally, we played two recorded performances, one was the winner and the other was a human performance, played by a concert artist and piano teacher. We told the assessors that they were listening the winner and another automatic performance and we asked them to express which one they prefer, by rising their hand.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Analysis of performances evaluation

The average ratings of the performances (part A of the assessment questionnaire), considering the total of the participants, the male and the females, are presented in Tab. 2. The range of ratings is large: E1, E2 and E3 were rated between 1 and 9. The performance E4 was rated between 3 and 9. In addition, 9 participants express their preference for E1; 6 for E2; 1 for E3; 7 for E4. Fig. 4 shows the boxplot of ratings with estimated density. All the distribution of the assessors rates were unimodal, but E2 which shows a bimodal distribution, probably indicating two distinct taste categories.

	E1	E2	E3	E4
Total (M)	6.78	5.52	3.91	6.59
Total (SD)	1.86	2.39	1.90	1.37
Female (M)	6.17	5.83	4.17	5.6
Female (SD)	1.17	3.19	2.64	1.95
Male (M)	7.00	5.41	3.82	6.88
Male (SD)	2.03	2.15	1.67	1.05

Table 2. Analysis of the part A of the assessment questionnaire on the total participants, on females and on males. Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD).

Fig. 5 shows the biplot computed from the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the performances ratings. We may notice that E2 is orthogonal to the other performances. In addition, we may observe that the assessors are clustered in three groups: (i) assessors that likes E2, (ii) assessors that likes E1, E3 and E4 and (iii) subjects that tend to refuse all the automatic performances.

Comments to the GATM performances are listed in Appendix B, divided in three categories, according to [16]. In some cases there is a total disagreement in the assessment of the same performance. E.g., E1 has been judged both “regular” and “irregular”; E4 sounds at the same time “very pleasant” and “not at all suitable”. Of course, many of these differences are due to the subjective nature of the evaluation of any artistic work. Others may depend from the experimental setup: the audience listened the entire performance only once, before to judge it, as in a live concert scenario. In some cases, this fact could be the cause of hasty and inaccurate judgments.

To better evaluate the subjective judgments of the public, we report some objective features calculated from the performances, regarding tempo and dynamics. Performance E1 has been played with an average tempo of 122 BPM; the middle section has been played at 108 BPM; a dynamic range of 40.6 dB with a maximum RMS amplitude of -13.46 dBFS. E2 is characterized by an average tempo of 132 BPM with a middle section at 124 BPM; a dynamic range of 49.4 dB and a maximum RMS amplitude of -9.9 dBFS. E3 has an average tempo of 102 with a middle part at 94; a dynamic range of 47.7 dB and a maximum RMS amplitude of -12.2 dBFS. Finally, E4 has been played at 128 BPM on average with a middle section at 88 BPM; a dynamic range of 47.0 dB and a maximum RMS amplitude of -12.5 dBFS.

Figure 5. Biplot of a Principal Component Analysis of the performance ratings in GATM experiment. Numbers represent the ID of each listener, whereas arrows represent the correlation among the systems.

Figure 6. Biplot of a Principal Component Analysis on the factors presented in part B1.

	b1a	b1b	b1c	b1d
Total (M)	4.23	5.09	5.27	5.39
Total (SD)	1.74	1.59	0.98	1.62
Female (M)	4.50	4.83	5.17	4.50
Female (SD)	2.07	1.60	0.98	2.07
Male (M)	4.13	5.18	5.31	5.71
Male (SD)	1.67	1.63	1.01	1.36

Table 3. Analysis of the factors (part B1 of the assessment questionnaire) on the total participants, on females and on males. Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD).

Comparing these values with the afore mentioned comments, it is possible to note that when there is an agreement among the subject, the judgment is often coherent with the measured features. E. g., many subjects agree in considering exaggerated the dynamic variations of performance E2, which actually has the greatest dynamic range. On the contrary, performance E1 is generally considered too scholastic and little expressive, probably due to the small dynamic and agogic differences.

The overall balance of the performances is not always considered sufficient by the assessors. This is due to the fact that the systems pay more attention to the phrasing levels, than to the interpretation of the song in its entirety. This comment can be a useful hint for systems developers.

Finally, there are some interesting comments characterized by a comparison with human performances. Despite the audience was aware that all the performances were computer generated, some subjects used verbal expressions such as “seems to remember an unmusical student”, “if it were a person it would seem inaccurate”, or “boy playing so fast because he likes run”, denoting the tendency to attribute to the automatic performances a human personality.

About the evaluation between E1 and the human performance: our experience has been that it is good, or at least interesting, to include a human performance among synthesized ones in the performances sample (and thus made

the experiment a bit more as a sort of a Turing test) because it gives a perspective of how far away or close to the ecologically valid performance the synthesized ones lie. The result is that the human one was very slightly preferred, by only one preferences. And this may be in favor to not exclude in the future a sort of Turing test like experiment.

4.4.2 Analysis of assessors’ preferences and cognitive style

The average rating of the factors that influence the enjoyment of the performances (part B1 of the assessment questionnaire, see Appendix A), considering all the participants, only male and only females, is listed in Tab. 3. It can be noticed that there are distinct genre behavior in factors b1b and b1d. The mean values are not quite distinct, apart factor b1a (related to technical accuracy of the performance) that received less importance: maybe the assessors, knowing that stimuli were generated performances, were less concerned by technical precision (b1a) and payed more attention to the interpretative factors.

Fig. 6 shows the biplot computed from the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the factors presented in the part B1. The first two components explains 49.4% and 24.8% of total variance. The factor b1a is orthogonal to b1d, as it was to be expected because b1a is related to technical aspects and b1c to emotional aspect.

Tab. 4 shows the ME and MS Simplified Unit Weight (SUW) values [9], describing the cognitive styles. The low empathising score (ME) reflects a philosophical/training/conditioning stance that some who are convinced that the role of music was not to express emotions – a ‘formalist’ perspective. This is particularly true in older generation analytic musicologists: it seems that this has been changing in the last couple of decades, at least in Anglo-Saxon school. Our experiment confirms this trend: the younger group is associated to a ME SUW value (-10.67), which is less negative than older group (-14.29).

MS scores: <i>music systemizing</i>					
	Total	Female	Male	Younger	Older
M	1.70	2.00	1.59	3.44	0.57
SD	7.47	5.62	8.18	4.22	8.95
M [9]	3.46	2.35	5.09		
SD [9]	8.04	7.93	8.09		
ME scores: <i>music empathizing</i>					
	Total	Female	Male	Younger	Older
M	-12.87	-14.00	-12.47	-10.67	-14.29
SD	10.39	10.81	10.55	12.70	8.80
M [9]	2.50	4.00	0.29		
SD [9]	7.20	5.89	8.47		

Table 4. Means (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) of music cognitive styles SUW scores [9] for all the assessors, male, female, younger (≤ 50 years) and older (> 50 years). All the data are compared with the results obtained by [9] for the “Professional” level of music performance experience (Mean [9] and SD [9]).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Two experiments, conducted during two dedicated workshops, were presented. The first one was carried out on a uneven population, the second one on a homogeneous population (musicology analysts). This allowed us to observe how this particular population stands on generated performances. The aim is to understand how the audience judges computer generated music performances. In particular, we analyzed possible different preferences and expectations of the listeners and influencing factors, such as cognitive styles.

The analysis of the ratings allows us to see (i) how preferences are distributed among the various performances and (ii) whether any orthogonalities and/or correlations exist.

If we compare the analysis of the factors in the two experiments, we can observe that general audience tends to give the same importance to emotional and technical factors (b6 and b7), and the difference depends on the remaining factors. On the contrary, for analyst audience, the emotional and technical factors (b1a and b1d) are very distinct and the remaining factors are situated between them.

It should be noted that, even if the performances are computer generated, there is a human contribution: in automatic systems this is given by the choice of the model and by the parameters (e.g., in the rules systems is given by the weights assigned to the rules); in interactive systems, in addition to the choice of the parameters, the contribution of the performer during the real-time control should also be considered. In this sense, the assessment includes also a judgment on the interpretative choices and depends on the experience of the assessors.

The analysis of the cognitive styles pointed out how the assessors stands on generated performances. The results of the GATM 2012 experiment show that all the assessors were systemizers, and young people had a less negative value of ME. It is important to conduct experiments with other populations of assessors, in order to point out the behavior of other typologies of assessors and study their preferences.

From the perspective of scientific progress, these judgments are useful not only for the purpose of ranking the systems but also for providing the researchers with information about the direction in which they should focus efforts to improve their systems. Specific measurements of performance quality can explicitly and precisely reveal the strengths and weaknesses of a system, and this information can, in turn, suggest short- and medium-term goals for improvement. This study helps to understand the relationship between art and technology.

Appendix A: Assessment questionnaire

There are many factors that can impact on one's enjoyment of a musical performance. The survey is intended to find out which of these are most important for you when you are listening to a generated music performance.

The survey is divided into three parts: part A must be filled after listening the music performances obtained by automatic methods. Parts B1 and B2 must be filled at the end.

The detailed instructions given to the participants are shown below.

PART A – *Instructions to fill the form:*

You will listen to four different generated performances, one after the other, of the same musical piece. Then the performances will be played again, one-by-one, and at the end of each performance you will be requested to fill the corresponding section. How much do you give applause to the performance? (1: nothing – 10: ovation)

PART B1 – *Instructions to fill the form:*

How much did the following factors influenced the (high or low) enjoyment of the listened generated performances?

1: no influence – 7: very high influence

b1a. Technical accuracy of the performance

b1b. Coherence with the concert performance style

b1c. Presence of choices that are original and interesting

b1d. Capacity of arousing an emotional involvement in the listener

Are there any other factors that are important in determining your personal enjoyment of the performance?

(If there are several, please list in order: most important → least important)

PART B2 – *Instructions to fill the form:*

This questionnaire is about the so-called cognitive style. Some people are slightly more interested in other people than they are, for example, in technology. For other people, the opposite is true. Either way, there is no 'right' or 'wrong' cognitive style in that sense. They can just be different.

Here we would like to invite you to fill in a questionnaire that will inform us about your cognitive style. The purpose of this research is to find out what aspects of music are more or less important to different people when listening to or thinking about music.

While filling in your responses, please read the lines carefully and circle the number in each line that is most appropriate for you: (1: completely disagree, 2: partially disagree, 3: partially agree, 4: completely agree).

The statements are the same presented in [9, Appendix B].

Appendix B: Assessors' comments to the GATM performances

Comments to the GATM performances divided in the three following categories, according to [16].

Technical mastery and control

E1: phrasing balanced, low dynamic range, little agogic, if it were a person it would seem inaccurate, mechanical, distinction legato/staccato, clumsy performance, regular, irregular, balanced but not rigid.

E2: extreme dynamics, excessive sforzato, boy playing so fast because he likes to run, too varied, non-flexible dynamic, little physical plausibility, inadequate ritardandi and rubati, performance more technical (professional?).

E3: the pianist strikes too strong, unacceptable grace notes, excessive appoggiaturas, too slow, laborious performance (student awkward?), misplaced accents and weighting, mechanical.

E4: little physical responses, little phrasing, tempo too slow in the second section, good tempo, too excessive agogic, rhythmic variations between phrases, some technical stumbling, full of swing, not perfect technically.

Sound quality

E1: effect of sound without weight, muffled timbre, weight left hand, timbre quality.

E2: bright.

E3: regular touch, softness, touch too hard, heavy sound.

E4: nice touch.

Convincing musical understanding

E1: beginner student, reliefs of the parts, fluid and with the right amount of irony, elegant, pleasant, little expressive, too scholastic, not too expressive, good the form, adequate for this kind of music, switable, expressive, elegant, monotonous, delicate, perhaps a bit too caressing.

E2: instinctive choices, scherzoso, almost gestural, exaggerated and awkward, look brilliant, rhapsodic, right alternation, interesting, makes the sense of burlesque, performance uneven.

E3: first reading, balance, out of style, performance quite expressive, very pleasant, not at all suitable, seems to remember an unmusical student, enjoyable, point to emotional communication, simulation of a scholastic performance, it is grainy, not unitary, rigid and cold, scholastic, disorganized, poorly developed phrasing, lack of elegance, inappropriate, inadequate to express correct emotions.

E4: nice, close to a human performance, passages more credible, makes concertistic the performance, good emotional communication, there is no balance, exaggerated changes, loss of equality, burlesque, but excessive, passages more credible, no unitary perception of the musical piece, balanced in the first part, emphatic the middle and the final parts, very natural, expressiveness acceptable, good ideas with moments mannerist.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kirke and E. R. Miranda, Eds., *Guide to Computing for Expressive Music Performance*. Springer-Verlag, 2012.
- [2] S. Canazza, G. De Poli, A. Rodà, and A. Vidolin, "Expressiveness in music performance: analysis, models, mapping, encoding," in *Structuring Music through Markup Language: Designs and Architectures*, J. Steyn, Ed. IGI Global, 2012, pp. 156–186.
- [3] R. Bresin and A. Friberg, "Evaluation of computer systems for expressive music performance," in *Guide to Computing for Expressive Music Performance*, A. Kirke and E. Miranda, Eds. London: Springer-Verlag, 2013, pp. 181–203.
- [4] R. Hiraga, M. Hashida, K. Hirata, H. Katayose, and K. Noike, "Rencon: towards a new evaluation method for performance," in *Proceedings of International Computer Music Conference (ICMC)*, Gothenburg, Sweden, 2002, pp. 357–360.
- [5] H. Katayose, M. Hashida, G. De Poli, and K. Hirata, "On evaluating systems for generating expressive music performance: the Rencon experience," *J. of New Music Research*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 299–310, 2012.
- [6] G. McPherson and W. Thompson, "Assessing music performances: Issues and influences," *Research Studies in Music Education*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 12–24, 1998.
- [7] S. Thompson and A. Williamon, "Evaluating evaluation: Musical performance assessment as a research tool," *Music Perception*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 21–41, 2003.
- [8] B. H. Repp, "The aesthetic quality of a quantitatively average music performance: two preliminary experiments," *Music Perception*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 419–444, 1997.
- [9] G. Kreutz, E. Schubert, and L. Mitchell, "Cognitive styles of music listening," *Music Perception*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 57–73, 2008.
- [10] S. Garrido and E. Schubert, "Personality and computer music," in *Proc. Sound and Music Comp. Conf.*, 2011.
- [11] G. Widmer, S. Flossmann, and M. Grachten, "YQX plays Chopin," *AI Magazine*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 35–48, 2009.
- [12] M. Grachten and G. Widmer, "Linear basis models for prediction and analysis of musical expression," *J. of New Music Research*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 311–322, 2012.
- [13] E. Bisesi, R. Parncutt, and A. Friberg, "An accent-based approach to performance rendering: Music theory meets music psychology," in *Proc. Symposium on Performance Science (ISPS 2011)*, 2011, pp. 27–32.
- [14] H. Katayose and K. Gakuin, "Using an expressive performance template in a music conducting interface," in *Proceedings of the 2004 Conf. on New Instruments for Musical Expression (NIME 2004)*, 2004, pp. 3–5.
- [15] S. Tanaka, M. Hashida, and H. Katayose, "Shunji: A case-based performance rendering system attached importance to phrase expression," in *Proc. Sound and Music Computing Conf. (SMC-11)*, 2011.
- [16] W. J. Wrigley and S. B. Emmerson, "Ecological development of a music performance rating scale for five instrument families," *Psychology of Music*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 97–118, 2013.